

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

Print: 3082-4060
Online: 3082-4079

VOLUME 1

ISSUE 3 | JULY - SEPTEMBER ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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Volume I, Issue III | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“WRITING STRUGGLES”

I'm not a writer.

I'm an editor, an illustrator, an actor.

Yet of the art forms I try to pursue,
Writing is a skill I somehow can't do.

I've been reading since I was small.

Tales of joy, adventure, wonder,
Or stories that'll make you bawl.

Can I create my own story? I pondered.

When I try to make stories I wish to share.

It just ends up going nowhere.

I string some words and my minds a mess,
Suddenly, I don't know how to connect.

Everything feels empty and uninspired,
my childhood passion suddenly expired.

Am I unable to write something complex?

Or am I just afraid to express?

Yes, that's it, that must be the key.

If not, then what else can it be?

That I'm a broken toy, incapable

Of pouring my love somewhere verbal?

I considered myself creative,

Now I don't know if that's true.

Is it normal to feel so defeated,

When there's a talent I can't do?

I hope there's a happy ending”

For this story, at least.

That I won't give up writing,

And my ink won't cease.

Just because I've crumpled up paper,
Doesn't mean that I'm a failure.
I'd rather lose my mind on an empty sheet,
Than lose heart and admit defeat.

